

Experimental methods

Chemicals

2-Mercaptobenzothiazole, p-aminobenzoic acid, 3-aminopropionic acid, 6-amino-hexanoic acid were purchased from Hyperchem/China. Ethyl chloroformate (ECF, CAS ID: 541-41-3), Hydroxylamine. HCl (CAS ID: 5470-11-1), Vorinostat (suberoylanilide hydroxamic acid, SAHA, CAS ID: 149647-78-9), L-Alanine (CAS ID: 56-41-7), L-Cysteine (CAS ID: 52-90-4), aminopropionic acid (CAS ID: 107-95-9), aminohexanoic acid (CAS ID: 60-32-2) and p-amino- benzoic acid (CAS ID: 150-13-0) were purchased from sigma/Aldrich (Germany). For cell culture studies all the investigated compounds were dissolved in Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO, 10 ml stocks) and were stored in a deep freezer at -20 °C. Experimentally, stocks were diluted in cell culture medium. The hybrid molecules were synthesized as described in details in the following sections.

Preparation of the investigated hybrid molecules

Hybrid molecules of benzothiazole cross-linked with hydroxamic acid through certain linkers, such as, L-alanine, L-cysteine, 3-aminopropionic acid, 6-aminohexanoic acid or p-aminobenzoic acid were proposed. These hybrid molecules were synthesized starting from 2-mercaptobenzo-thiazole, which is S-alkylated with bromoacetic acid leading to the formation of benzothiazole containing a side chain with a sulfide and a carboxyl group, as called the intermediate (*2-(benzo- [d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetic acid*). The chemical structures of the new hybrids (**Scheme 1**) and their SMILES (Simplified Molecular-Input Line-Entry Systems) notations were constructed using Chemdraw ultra 10.0. Vorinostat (SAHA) was used as the reference ligand.

Molecular docking

Molecular docking was performed using the Maestro software (Schrödinger, version 2023-1) and the ΔG (kcal/mol) values, as the docking scores function representing the energy required for binding to receptor, were calculated. The chemical structure of HDAC8 type 1T69 was retrieved from protein data bank, PDB, website (<https://www.rcsb.org>) and

imported to Maestro software program. They were processed and their energy were minimized by the protein preparation workflow module. Through this process, unnecessary metals (except Zn^{+2} ions), ligands (except SAHA, which is the reference ligand), enzyme chains (except chain A), and the water molecules were deleted. The Grid was generated by the Receptor Grid Generator module, during which the binding site was defined by SAHA. The lowest docking scores, as ΔG (kcal/mol), for the investigated compounds and their images, which showed the interaction of each compound with Zn^{2+} ions and the amino acid residues in the binding site. Docking scores and visualization images of ligand-receptor complexes were shown on **Table 1** and **Figure 1**. These hybrids were treated as successful candidates that have the highest binding affinities based on the lowest docking scores (ΔG , Kcal/mole).

General methods

Melting points were determined (uncorrected) using electrical melting point apparatus, Electro-thermal 9300, USA. The infrared spectra were recorded in KBr disc by FT-IR spectrophotometer / Shimadzu. 1H -NMR and ^{13}C -NMR spectra were recorded using NMR Bruker 500 MHz-Avance III spectrometer and the chemical shifts were recorded in parts per million (ppm). Tetramethylsilane was used as the reference.

Chemical synthesis

Chemical synthesis of the intermediate (2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetic acid

This compound is synthesized through S-alkylation reaction of 2-mercaptobenzothiazole with α -bromoacetic acid, and as follows;

To a stirred aqueous solution of α -bromoacetic acid (10mmol, 1.389g) in sodium hydroxide solution (10%, 10 mL), 2-mercaptobenzothiazole (10mmol, 1.6725g) in an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (10%, 10 mL) was added drop wise with continuous stirring. The mixture was refluxed for 3hrs and was then cooled and acidified with diluted hydrochloric acid to obtain a precipitate, which was filtered, washed excessively with distilled water and crystallized from ethanol to afford a yield of 90%, as white powder, m.p. 152-153 °C, as depicted on **Figure 1**.

FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3110-2513 (str. vib. of OH of COOH), 3074 (Str. vib. of C-H aromatic ring), 2956-2896 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1714

(str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1602-1581-1498 (str. vib. of C=C aromatic ring), 1315 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH).

General procedure for the synthesis of BZT-Linker (1A-E)

These compounds were prepared using the mixed anhydride method ¹⁷, as depicted in **Figure 1**, and as follows;

The intermediate (2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetic acid (10mmol) was suspended in dry chloroform (40ml) containing triethylamine (TEA, 10 mmol) and the mixture was cooled to (-5 to -8 °C) in an ice bath. Ethyl chloroformate (10 mmol) was added dropwise during 15 min and the mixture was stirred for further 15 min. The linker (10mmol) was dissolved in a cold distilled water containing TEA (10mmol) and was added immediately all at once with vigorous stirring for 1hr in an ice bath and for further 3hrs at room temperature. A two-layered yellowish-orange solution was obtained, which was separated using a separator funnel and the aqueous layer was removed. The chloroform layer was washed with distilled water (3 x 20 ml) and was dried with anhydrous magnesium sulfate, filtered and evaporated under reduced pressure in a rotary evaporator to obtain yellowish-orange residues. The residues were washed with diethyl ether or petroleum ether few times to afford crystalline powder representing the resultant products (**1A-E**). The purity of the target compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography using cyclohexane: chloroform (50:50) solvent system. These compounds were synthesized and collected as follows:

BZT-Linker-Ala 1A {(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetyl) alanine (C₁₂H₁₂O₃N₂S₂, 296.36 g/mole)} was synthesized starting from the intermediate (2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetic acid) and L-alanine (10mmol, 1.6g), as red crystalline powder, m.p. 165-167 °C with 79% yield. FT-IR spectra (ν, cm⁻¹) recorded the following characterized bands; 3461 (str. vib. of OH-COOH), 3419 (str. vib. of NH-amide), 2954-2905 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1712 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1668 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1589-1573-1479 (str. vib. of C=C aromatic ring).

BZT-Linker-Cys 1B {(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetyl) cysteine (C₁₂H₁₂O₃N₂S₃, 328.42 g/mole)} was prepared using L-Cysteine (10mmol, 1.2g) and collected as yellow crystalline powder, m.p. 175-177 °C with 85% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the

following bands; 3461 (str. vib. of OH-COOH), 3288 (str. vib. of NH-amide), 3062 (str. vib. of C-H aromatic ring), 2912-2871 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym), 1714 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1641 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1600-1545 (str. vib. of C=C aromatic ring).

Compound 1C {3-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido) propionic acid

(C₁₂H₁₂O₃N₂S₂, 296.36) was prepared by reacting the intermediate with 3-amino-propionic acid (10mmol, 1.6g) and collected as orange powder, m.p. 210-212 °C with 76% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3442 (str. vib. of OH-COOH), 3225 (str. vib. of NH amide), 3050 (str. vib. of CH arom), 2987-2858 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym), 1724 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1631 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1600-1514 (str. vib. of C=C arom).

BZT-Linker-Aminohexanoic acid 1D {6-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido)

hexanoic acid (C₁₅H₁₈O₃N₂S₂, 338 g/mole)} was prepared starting from the intermediate and 6-aminohexanoic acid (10mmol, 1.31g) and collected as orange powder, m.p. 225-227 °C with 90% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3427 (str. vib. of OH-COOH), 3271 (str. vib. of NH of amide), 3075 (str. vib. of C-H arom), 2983-2873 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym), 1737 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1629 (str. vib. of C=O of amid), 1612-1581 (str. vib. of C=C arom).

BZT-Linker-p-Aminobenzoic acid 1E {4-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido)

benzoic acid (C₁₆H₁₂O₃N₂S₂, 344.4 g/mole)} was prepared from the intermediate and p-aminobenzoic acid (10mmol, 1.37g) and collected as purple powder, m.p. 180-182 °C with 70% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3430 (str. vib. of OH-COOH), 3330 (str. vib. of NH of amide), 3026 (str. vib. of C-H arom), 2981-2937 (str. vib. of C-H arom), 1703 (str. vib. of C=O of COOH), 1641 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1598-1558-1479 (str. vib. of C=C arom).

General procedure for synthesis of the hybrid molecules (2A-E)

The target hybrid molecules were prepared starting with compounds **1A-E** and reacted with hydroxylamine to afford the hybrid molecules **2A-E**, as depicted in [scheme 1](#). This reaction was performed using the modified mixed anhydride method (**17**), as previously described. Compounds **1A-E** (10mmol) in dry chloroform containing TEA (10mmol) was reacted with ECF (10mmol) and was then reacted with hydroxylamine. HCl (10mmol) in

an aqueous solution (10ml) containing TEA (10mmol). The target compounds were excessively washed with diethyl ether and petroleum ether to afford crystalline powder representing the resultant products (**2A-E**). The purity of the hybrid molecules was checked by thin layer chromatography using cyclohexane: chloroform (50:50) mobile phase.

BZT-Linker-Ala Hydroxamate (2A) {2-(2-(benzo- [d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido)-N-Hydroxypropanamide ($C_{12}H_{13}O_3N_3S_2$, 311.37 g/mole) was synthesized by reaction of compound **1A** (10mmol, 2.964 g) with aminopropionic acid (10mmole, 0.89 g) and was collected as yellow powder, m.p. 253-255 °C with 80% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3452 (OH str. vib. of oxime), 3257 (NH str. vib. of oxime), 3200 (NH str. vib. of amide), 3058 (str. vib. of C-H arom), 2983-2852 (str. vib. of C-H aliph, asym and sym), 1699 (str. vib. of C=O of oxime), 1616 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1610-1569 (str. vib. of C=C arom). 1H -NMR spectra recorded the followings signals (δ , ppm); 1.28 (doublet, 3H, CH_3), 4.25 (quartet, 1H, CH), 4.92 (singlet, 2H, CH_2), 7.40- 8.35 (multiplate, 4H, represent phenyl), 8.85 (singlet 1H, NH of amide group), 9.20 (singlet 1H, NH of oxime group), 10.96 (singlet, 1H, OH group). ^{13}C -NMR spectra recorded the followings signals; 13.67 (CH_3), 34.59 (CH), 61.50 (CH_2), 111.91-125.83 (arom. CH), 152.58 (C=N of benzothiazole), 164.54 (C=O of amide), 168.08 (C=O of oxime).

BZT-Linker-Cys Hydroxamate (2B) {2-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido)-N-hydroxy-3-mercaptopropanamide ($C_{12}H_{13}O_3N_3S_3$, 343.43 g/mole) was synthesized starting from compound **1B** (10mmol, 3.284 g) and was collected as paige-colored powder, m.p. 235-237 °C with 77% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following characteristic bands; 3431 (str. vib. of OH-oxime), 3290 (NH str. vib. of oxime), 3114 (str. vib. of NH-amide), 3078 (str. vib. of C-H aromatic ring), 2964-2894 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym), 1699 (str. vib. of C=O of oxime), 1639 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1596-1554-1496 (str. vib. of C=C arom.). 1H -NMR spectra (δ , ppm) showed the following signals; 3.48 (singlet, 1H, SH), 4.50 (triplet, 1H, CH), 4.13 (doublet, 2H, CH_2), 4.88 (singlet, 2H, CH_2), 7.37-8.10 (multiplate, 4H, phenyl), 8.27 (singlet, 1H, NH of amide group), 8.82 (singlet, 1H, NH of oxime group), 10.81 (singlet, 1H, OH group).

¹³C-NMR spectra recorded the following signals; 39.66 (CH₂-SH), 40.78 (CH), 41.23 (CH₂), 124.86-135.25 (CH arom), 153.32 (C=N of benzothiazole), 158.61 (C=O of amide), 167.27 (C=O of oxime).

BZT-Linker-Aminopropionic acid (2C) {3-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido)-N-hydroxypropanamide (C₁₂H₁₃O₃N₃S₂, 311.37 g/mole) was prepared starting from compound **1C** (10mmol, 2.964 g) and was collected as dark brown powder, m.p. 219-221 °C with 88% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3315 (OH str. vib. of oxime), 3188 (NH str. vib. of oxime), 3112 (NH str. vib. of amide), 3053 (str. vib. of C-H arom.), 2981-2837 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1704 (str. vib. of C=O of oxime), 1679 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1600-1531-1500 (str. vib. of C=C arom.). ¹H-NMR spectra (δ, ppm) showed the following signals; 2.16 (triplet, 2H, CH₂-C=O), 3.58 (triplet, 2H, CH₂-N), 4.32 (singlet, 2H, CH₂-S), 7.32-8.20 (multiplate, 4H, phenyl), 8.90 (singlet, 1H, NH of amide), 8.94 (singlet, 1H, NH of oxime), 9.86 (singlet, 1H, OH). ¹³C-NMR spectra recorded the following signals; 19.05 (CH₂-C=O), 38.30 (CH₂-N), 56.53 (CH₂-S), 119.31-129.34 (CH arom), 152.97 (C=N of benzothiazole), 166.37 (C=O of amide), 166.59 (C=O of oxime).

BZT-Linker-Aminohexanoic acid (2D) {6-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio) acetamido)-N-hydroxyhexanamide (C₁₅H₁₉O₃N₃S₂, 353.45 g/mol) was synthesized from compound **1D** (10mmol, 3.38 g) and was collected as chocolate-color powder, m.p. 269-271 °C with 85% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 34446 (str. vib. of OH-oxime), 3359 (str. vib. of NH-oxime), 3184 (NH str. vib. of amide), 3060 (str. vib. of C-H arom.), 2985-2918 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1704 (str. vib. of C=O of oxime), 1649 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1599-1583 (str. vib. of C=C arom.). ¹H-NMR spectra (δ, ppm) showed the following signals; 1.25-2.11 (multiplate, 6H, 3(CH₂)), 4.14 (triplet, 2H, CH₂-C=O), 4.19 (triplet, 2H, CH₂-N), 4.87 (singlet, 2H, CH₂-S), 7.35-8.05 (multiplate, 4H, phenyl), 8.32 (singlet, 1H, NH of amide), 8.86 (singlet, 1H, NH of oxime), 10.20 (singlet, 1H, OH). ¹³C-NMR spectra showed the following signals; 13.78 (CH₂), 18.25 (CH₂), 20.89 (CH₂), 24.60 (CH₂ C=O), 35.86 (CH₂-N), 55.86 (CH₂-S), 111.86-134.90 (CH arom), 151.03 (C=N of benzothiazole), 158.84 (C=O of amide), 162.32 (C=O of oxime).

BZT-Linker-p-Aminobenzoic acid Hydroxamate (2E) {4-(2-(benzo[d]thiazol-2-yl-thio)acetamido)-N-Hydroxy benzamide (C₁₆H₁₃O₃N₃S₂, 359.42 g/mole) was prepared starting from compound **1E** (10mmol, 3.44 g) and was collected as white powder, m.p. 280-282 °C with 90% yield. FT-IR spectra recorded the following bands; 3444 (OH str. vib. of oxime), 3404 (NH str. vib. of oxime), 3295 (NH str. vib. of oxime), 3022 (str. vib. of C-H arom), 2972-2925 (str. vib. of C-H aliph. (asym and sym)), 1685 (str. vib. of C=O of oxime), 1625 (str. vib. of C=O of amide), 1597-1546 (str. vib. of C=C arom). ¹H-NMR spectra (δ, ppm) showed the following signals; 4.12 (singlet, 2H, CH₂-S), 7.28-7.30 (doublet, 2H, CH far C=O), 7.31-7.82 (multiplet, 4H, CH of benzothiazole), 7.91-7.94 (doublet, 2H, CH near C=O), 8.35 (singlet, 1H, NH of amide group), 9.35 (singlet, 1H, NH of oxime), 10.78 (singlet, 1H, OH). ¹³C-NMR spectra recorded the following signals; 41.12 (CH₂-S), 116.28-137.12 (CH arom), 153.61 (C=N of benzothiazole), 158.62 (C=O of amide), 167.22 (C=O of oxime).

Cell Culture

Detailed information as well as culture and MTT seeding conditions for used cell lines are provided. All cells were grown under standard cell culture conditions and regularly checked for mycoplasma contamination. The medium was supplemented with 10% fetal bovine calf serum.

Cell viability assays

Cells were plated (depending on the cell model 2–7x 10³ cells/well) in 96-well plates and allowed to recover for 24 h, 48 h and 72 h. Subsequently, the indicated drugs or their combinations were added. After 72 h exposure, the proportion of viable cells was determined by MTT assay¹⁸. Cytotoxicity was expressed as IC₅₀ (μg/ml) values calculated from full dose-response curves using Graph Pad Prism 8 software. The new hybrid molecules (**2A-E**) were tested for their anticancer activities using a colorimetric assay on the A549 human lung cancer cell¹⁸. MTT stock solution was added and the mixture was stored to generate purple formazan crystals for 2-4 h at 37°C. MTT solution was correctly disposed, formazan crystal was mixed in DMSO (100μl) containing SDS (10%) and acetic acid (1%). To completely dissolve the formazan crystals, the plates were agitated on the top of a shaker for 10 min. The procedure was done in 96-well flat

plates at different concentrations (500-0.97 μM) of the investigated compounds and the IC_{50} values were calculated after treating the cells with the compounds for 24, 48 and 72 hrs. Cell culture medium was carefully removed after being treated with the hybrids. The optical density was obtained at 570 nm and a Safire 2 Microplate reader were used to calculate the concentrations. The experiments were carried out in triplicate independently. The results are presented on **Table 4**. The dose-response curves were done by Prism Pad 9 using nonlinear regression analysis for the synthesized molecules using A549 cells are shown on **Figure 3**.